

Microgram Determination of Lead(II) using 2-Thioorotic Acid (Ammonium Salt) : Application to Steel Plant Effluent

NANDITA SHUKLA^a, J. K. MOITRA^a and G. S. PANDEY^b

^aCentral Pollution Control Board, East Arjun Nagar, Delhi-110 032

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Pt. Ravishankar Shukla University, Raipur-492 010

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There are several methods of determination of lead¹. The widely used methods are the spectrophotometric method using dithiozone and the atomic absorption spectrophotometric method. These methods require costly instruments and sophisticated technique². The present work illustrates a convenient, cheap and reliable method which may prove useful for pollution monitoring and drinking water quality survey with limited resources. This method involves conductometric titration based on the exclusive property of Pb^{II} ions forming PbF⁺ ions in the presence of fluoride ions. The PbF⁺ ions on reaction with ammonium salt of 2-thioorotic acid form 2-thioortate salt and the stoichiometric completion of the reaction is detectable by conductometric measurements³.

Results and Discussion

The results of determination of lead at different concentrations are presented in Table 1.

Effect of pH and diverse ions : The neutral state of the medium has been found to be the preferred state, but accuracy is unaffected in the pH range 6.0–7.5. At lower pH the error increases on account of separation of insoluble 2-thioorotic acid from the solution. The pH value higher than 7.5 has a solubling effect over the precipitated lead complex. Ag^I, Hg^{II}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cd^{II} and Fe^{II} form insoluble complexes and interfere. However in the presence of fluoride ions, except Ag^I all other ions are masked. A seven-fold concentration of the titrant over the substrate has been found to be optimum.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF Pb AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS

Pb taken µg dm ⁻³	Pb found µg dm ⁻³	Error %
1000	993	0.7
500	495	1.0
100	99	1.0
50	49	2.0

Application : Homogenised sample of Bhilai Steel Plant waste water (open hearth and blast furnace section) was collected and found to have the following characteristics : pH, 6.8; sulphate, 85; chloride, 135; nitrate, 12; Ca, 142; Mg, 22; Na, 158; K, 36; Fe, 8; Cu, 1.4; Zn, 2 and Cr, 0.5 (all values in mg dm⁻³). Ni, Co, Ag, Hg and Cd were not detectable in the effluent².

For the estimation of lead in waste water, the aliquot (10 ml) was diluted to 50 ml using distilled water and the procedure was followed as above. The same effluent was analysed for lead content using spectrophotometric method (dithiozone) and atomic absorption spectrophotometric method and the results are compared in Table 2.

TABLE 2 – ESTIMATION OF Pb IN WASTE WATER SAMPLE USING DIFFERENT METHODS

Method	Concn. determined mg dm ⁻³
Present	0.35
Spectrophotometric	0.30
AAS	0.36

* Average of three replicate determinations.

Experimental

1,2-Thioorotic acid (100 mg) was dissolved in minimum volume of concentrated ammonia solution and evaporated gently to dryness. The resulting ammonium salt was dissolved in distilled water (100 ml); a workable solution (4 mg dm^{-3}) was prepared by diluting with distilled water. A solution of NaF was prepared containing 0.5 mg dm^{-3} fluoride.

Lead solution (prepared by dissolving 100 mg pure lead metal in a mixture of 2 ml concentrated HNO_3 and 2 ml distilled water) was appropriately diluted to obtain a workable standard of 0.1 mg dm^{-3} .

Procedure : Four working standards of lead solution containing 50, 100, 500 and $1000 \mu\text{g dm}^{-3}$ Pb were prepared. Thereafter NaF solution was added to the magnetically stirred above solution till almost a linear increase in the conductance values was observed. This confirmed that the uptake of the requisite amount of fluoride in the formation of PbF^+ ions. Then the solution containing PbF^+ ions was titrated conductometrically using 2-thioorotic

acid reagent. The equivalence points were determined from the volume-conductance graph. The results are shown in Table 1.

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